

NUMBER OF TOURIST ARRIVALS TO UZBEKISTAN BETWEEN 2017 AND 2023

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Abstract. *Tourism is one of the most strategic and developing sector of national economy of Uzbekistan. This study aims to investigate number of tourist arrivals in the tourism sector of Uzbekistan in 2017 and 2023. It outlines key changes during the period of these years, it identifies development of tourism and touristic destination and analyze number of tourist arrivals to Uzbekistan. And highlights impacts of COVID-19 to economic sector and pandemic period.*

Key words: *tourist arrivals, Tourism sector, Touristic destination, Covid-19.*

Annotatsiya. *Turizm O'zbekiston milliy iqtisodiyotining strategik muhim va rivojlanayotgan tarmoqlaridan biridir. Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi 2017 va 2023 yillarda O'zbekistonning turizm sektoriga kelgan turistlar sonini o'rganishdan iborat. Unda ushbu yillardagi asosiy o'zgarishlar belgilab berilgan, turizm va turistik yo'nalishlarning rivojlanishi belgilab berilgan, shuningdek, O'zbekistonga kelgan sayyohlar soni tahlil qilingan. Va COVID-19 ning iqtisodiy sektor va pandemiya davriga ta'sirini ta'kidlaydi.*

Kalit so'zlar. *turistlarning kelishi, Turizm sektori, Turistik manzil, Covid-19.*

Аннотация. *Туризм является одним из наиболее стратегически важных и развивающихся секторов национальной экономики Узбекистана. Целью данного исследования является изучение количества туристических прибытий в туристический сектор Узбекистана в 2017 и 2023 годах. В нем излагаются ключевые изменения за период этих лет, определяется развитие туризма и туристических направлений, а также анализируется количество туристических прибытий в Узбекистан. И подчеркивает влияние COVID-19 на экономический сектор и период пандемии.*

Ключевые слова: *туристические прибытия, Туристический сектор, Туристическое направление, Covid-19.*

Uzbekistan located in the heart of Silk Road. It is famous for its culture, rich history, majestic architecture and monuments, delicious cuisine, a variety of climate and nature. Tourist's interest in Uzbekistan has remarkably travel facilities and high quality of services. However, the number of people intrigued in this mysterious country from year to year. Uzbekistan is a country where hundreds of old monuments and historical buildings located. Majority of historical buildings located in Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, and Kokand. These cities are the main centers of tourism.

Studies on tourism issues appeared in the second half of the 20th century. Questions of the conceptual apparatus, theoretical and methodological nature on the problems of tourism and tourist activities are covered in the works of V.I. Azara, M.B. Birzhakova [1], I.V. Zorin, A.C. Kuskova, E.V. Listvy, V.L. Odintsova, Yu.S. Putrika, B.C. Senina. The works of Panov I.N. [2], Fowler, B. [3], Balaeva A., Predvoditeleva M. [4], Veprentsev V. [5], Dumazedier J. [6], Kozielski J. [7] are devoted to the problems of the development of international tourism. A significant contribution to the study of regional development and promotion of international tourism at the regional level made their work: Mac Cannell, D. [8], Rojek Ch. [9] and Toffler A. [10]. In addition, I would like to mention the research of Kanevsky I., Kuznetsova O. and Chirkina V., addressed to the role issue state in the development of tourism. Insufficient knowledge of modern tourism, additional

economic studies are needed that will reveal the place of tourism in the domestic service sector, identify the signs, current problems and the most significant factors of its development, as well as determine the most comprehensive structure of national tourism.

This study highlights general information about tourism in Uzbekistan and analyzing tourist arrivals from 169 nations between 2017 and 2023. After discussing the the used data specification and methodology, the research mentions policy implication and conclusion.

Data and Methodology

The research explores tourist arrivals to Uzbekistan and the data have been collected by referring to different sources.

Tourist arrivals to Uzbekistan between 2017 and 2023

Figure 1

Year	Number of tourists (million)
2017	2.7
2018	5.3
2019	6.7
2020	1.5
2021	1.9
2022	5.7
2023(projected)	7

The table illustrates number of visitors to Uzbekistan in 7 years (2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, and 2023) 2.7 million tourists visited to Uzbekistan in 2017 and 2018 was quickly increased to 5.3 million. Also in 2019 tourist arrivals rapidly rised to 6.7 million. The industry earned a total of \$1.68 billion in that year. In 2020 and 2021 the figures shows dramatically decreased to 1.5 and 1.9 million. The reason for that COVID-19 and pandemic around the world. Not only Uzbekistan but also all countries tourist arrivals significantly dropped in that years. After the pandemic in 2022 tourist arrivals considerably increased to 5.7 million. In this year, the table shows sharply increased to 7 million. It is expected that by end of 2023 this number will reach approximately 7.2 million. Overall, tourism recovered 87% of pre-pandemic levels in January to September.

According to Statistics Agency, citizens of following countries visited for tourism purposes in Uzbekistan:

- Tajikistan – 958.5 thousand
- Kyrgyzstan – 786.4 thousand
- Kazakhstan – 764.4 thousand
- Russia – 345 thousand
- Turkey – 48.3 thousand
- Turkmenistan – 29.5 thousand
- India – 16.7 thousand
- Korea – 15.9 thousand
- China – 13.3 thousand
- Germany – 11.7 thousand

Uzbekistan tourist attraction categories

Figure 2

Categories	Percentage
Bazar or shopping	4.4%
Landmark	3.3%
Museum or theatre	12.2%
Religious or historic site	65.6%

The figure shows tourist attraction categories which more appealing places for foreign visitors in Uzbekistan. There are differences in four of the categories percentage. The largest one is Religious or historical places (65.6%). That means majority of tourists interested in our history and religion. For example: According to the department for tourism development of Samarkand region more than 239 thousand foreign visitors visited to Samarkand. Uzbekistan attracts 12.2% of tourist with its culture that means, museum and theatre shows our culture and our nationality. The next category is bazar or shopping centers, some of tourist go to bazar in order to buy our national clothes, dishes, or souvenirs. This figure shows only 4.4%. Due to the low percent, government try to improve range of bazar and shopping places. Most of tourists would like to go to historical places rather than bazar or shopping malls. Landmarks is significantly lower than other categories in Uzbekistan at just (3.3%).

RESULT

Before the COVID-19 travel and tourism were one of the most important sector of the economy. Tourism industry earned a total of \$1.68 billion before the pandemic in 2019. On the one hand, tourist numbers and revenue significantly impacted by the COVID-19. Due to the pandemic since 2020 Uzbekistan stopped all air and rail communication. It caused dropping tourism industry and hotel industry as well in both years 2020 and 2021. As discussed before, the number of tourist visited to Uzbekistan almost 1.5 million in 2020 during the pandemic. If compared with 2019, tourist arrivals decreased to 60%. As well as pandemic effected all economic sectors all around the world. This negative impact may lead to bankrupt and layoff. It can be concluded that tourism can play a big role in the economy. Tourism make a recovery 87% of pre-pandemic levels in this year. It is expected that, this percentage reach approximately 90% by the end of 2023.

CONCLUSION

The main purpose of this study was explore the tourist flows to Uzbekistan during the 7 years. The findings of this study summarized Figure 1 and analyzed number of tourist arrivals between 2017 and 2023. According to research pandemic period negative effected to tourism industry and all economic sectors.

In a globalized world tourism industry is developing day by day. Tourism creates many jobs, expands infrastructure, grows cultural exchange between citizens and foreigners. Uzbekistan has a potential to develop all types of tourism. Especially, cultural and historical tourism. Because there are so many historical cities in Uzbekistan such as, Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Kokand. This historical places attract more tourists attention rather than other tourist destination and other types of tourism.

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